

From Traditional Automation to Collaborative Robotics in Fine Robotic Assembly: a Case Study at i-Labs

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Abstract—In a rapidly changing industrial environment, the adoption of new technologies such as collaborative robotics and 3D printing often meets resistance, mainly due to concerns about not maintaining existing efficiency and quality standards. This paper proposes a paradigm shift in the implementation of assembly operations, normally entrusted to automatic machines specifically designed to meet stringent mechanical requirements, exploring the application of collaborative robots as an alternative. Empirical data and significant results are presented to highlight the potential and benefits of using these advanced technologies.

Index Terms—Collaborative Robots, 3D Printing, Technology Transfer, Assembly, Automation

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics and industrial automation generally coexist within production environments in order to exploit their respective complementary functions. In fact, when the industrial target requires repetitive tasks that are fast and executed over long periods of time, traditional automation is preferred, while robotics, because of its very high reconfigurability, performs better when the production plant is required to be more flexible.

The challenges industry faces today are different from those of the past, when products were more standardized. The current demand for customized products requires industry to be flexible in reconfiguring its production facilities [1]. To achieve this goal, the use of collaborative robots and 3D printing can greatly improve the versatility of the company, although this choice can generally lead to slower production.

Collaborative robots, or cobots, improve Industry 4.0 by helping workers perform tasks that require physical effort, thereby reducing work-related musculoskeletal disorders. They also improve task efficiency by establishing optimal trajectories and restricted zones [2].

3D printing, also known as digital fabrication or additive manufacturing, involves creating objects layer by layer from CAD models. It is commonly used in fields such as healthcare, automotive, and aerospace, and allows for mass customization and the use of different materials [3]

Fig. 1. Sub-component of the assembly study. On the left, an actual image of the component; on the right, a section of it

Fig. 2. Simplified operational diagram of the subcomponent assembly process

This paper presents a case study conducted at the i-Labs Industry Laboratory in Jesi (Italy), which addressed a challenging operation of fine robotic assembly.

The paper is organised as follows: the first part introduces the topic of the study, the second part reports the results and lessons learned, and finally conclusions and perspectives for future work are presented.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE PERFORMED WORK

A. Description

The task at hand involved the assembly of a subcomponent of a product, as shown in figure 1.

Previously, the assembly was done manually by an operator who assembled the different parts of the component one by one. The diagram illustrated in figure 2 shows the sequence of steps required to assemble the component.

Fig. 3. Rendering of the gripper and end fingers for the assembly process

The “Pick & Place” and positioning operations are highlighted in green, whereas the most critical assembly operations are marked in red.

B. Workflow

The workflow for this project was as follows:

- 1) identify the customer’s requirements (in this case, the customer was more interested in robotizing the process, even at the expense of increased cycle time, than in achieving partial automation);
- 2) define the tools to be used and the operating environment;
- 3) develop a functional design of the process;
- 4) perform initial assembly testing;
- 5) analyze and refine the project until the desired result is achieved;
- 6) completion.

The component shown in the figure 1 could be assembled in a completely automated manner by using the robot as a subordinate machine. However, the goal of the present work is to show that such assembly operation can also be carried out entirely by a collaborative robot.

III. RESULTS

The work performed has resulted in the successful completion of the full assembly of the component, leading to the definition of:

- the sequence of operations to be performed by the robot;
- the design of a multifunctional gripping system (robot fingers);
- the actual cycle time for the assembly process;
- the solutions and adjustments needed to improve the reliability of the system.

Figure 3 shows the assembled gripping system, consisting of the clamp and the designed fingers. These fingers are designed for different tasks within the assembly process and have a complex shape to meet the different requirements of the assembly operations.

Figure 4 shows the laboratory equipment used to test the entire assembly process. To test the convenience of programming directly on the tablet Teach Pendant (TP), the entire program was created in the TP language. According to the

Fig. 4. The set-up used for the test can be seen in this picture. The gripper shown is an older version of the final gripper used for assembly, shown in 3

authors, this method of programming on the FANUC CRX 10iA/L is useful and intuitive to learn, even for people with low programming knowledge. In addition, it is also possible to program applications that require a certain level of precision via TP using convergent adjustments, which means you set a rough position and then make small adjustments directly on the tablet. The ability to operate existing functions directly on the tablet simplifies access to software maintenance and reduces the time spent on code changes due to minor adjustments.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Thanks to this work, the company was able to make an informed assessment of options for improving its production process. The study not only provided a possible solution to the problem, but also brought to light some important aspects, such as that the removal and insertion of the ring is also possible through a fully robotic solution. However, this step is very critical and a more detailed evaluation is needed.

In view of digital manufacturing and the creation of flexible frameworks, explained in [4], the authors intend to implement in the future a vision system that identifies the approximate position of the various elements to be assembled and controls the most critical parts of the assembly through force feedback.

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